

Challenges Faced by College Students: An Exploratory Sequential Mixed Methods Study

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Abstract

College students often face personal and academic challenges that interfere with their ability to perform well and succeed in their studies. While prior studies have examined these issues, few have integrated both qualitative and quantitative data to gain deeper and more valid results. To address this gap, the present study employed a sequential explanatory design to explore and measure the common challenges experienced by college students. In the qualitative phase, one-on-one chat-based interviews were conducted with 25 purposively selected students from different year levels. Thematic analysis revealed key areas of difficulty, including academic pressure, emotional stress, financial struggles, time management problems, and learning difficulties. These themes were used to develop a survey instrument for the quantitative phase, which was administered online via Google Forms. A total of 281 responses were collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics. A merging approach was used to integrate findings from both phases through a joint display. Results showed that academic pressure, particularly fear of failure (88.26%), exam overload (68.33%), high academic expectations (62.99%), and performance anxiety (62.28%) were the most frequently experienced challenges. Emotional stress, time management difficulties, and financial issues were also prominent. The study highlights the interconnection between academic, emotional, and financial challenges and provides a basis for policymakers, school leaders, and educators to develop actions that respond to the actual needs of students.

Keywords: college student, challenges, mixed methods, exploratory sequential.

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Introduction

Education is often seen as a pathway to better opportunities, and college serves as a bridge between schooling and future careers. College life offers students a chance to grow, gain knowledge, and prepare for the real world. However, not all students have an easy experience. Many college students face different challenges that can affect their

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academic performance and overall well-being (Dagdag et al., 2019; Slimmen et al., 2022; Udhayakumar & Illango, 2023).

Based on the existing body of knowledge, common challenges faced by college students are diverse and interconnected. These include academic-related stress such as fear of failing, overwhelming workload, and frequent assessments (Akhtar & Akhtar, 2024; Saeed et al., 2020); emotional and mental health concerns like anxiety, especially during the second year (Wagner et al., 2025; Rabbi & Islam, 2024); and adjustment difficulties in navigating new academic and social environments (Akhtar & Akhtar, 2024; Saeed et al., 2020). Other issues include interpersonal and intrapersonal stressors, peer pressure, and self-doubt (Bashir et al., 2019); financial constraints (Bashir et al., 2019; Saeed et al., 2020); ineffective instructional practices and strained teacher-student relationships (Saeed et al., 2020); and the lack of tailored mental health and academic support systems (Wagner et al., 2025; Rabbi & Islam, 2024).

In the local context, Filipino college students commonly face challenges related to academic workload and difficulty (Dy et al., 2015; Dagdag et al., 2019; Austria-Cruz, 2019), including pressure from demanding subject matter, multiple responsibilities, and the need to balance academics with extracurricular commitments. They also report high levels of academic-related stress and emotional strain, often linked to teacher-related factors such as ineffective instruction or poor classroom management (Austria-Cruz, 2019; Dagdag et al., 2019). In addition, personal and financial difficulties, which include low self-confidence, family commitments, and lack of internet access, have been shown to disrupt learning (Dagdag et al., 2019; Agum et al., 2021). There is also a noted lack of activities that support holistic student development and promote effective learning habits (Dagdag et al., 2019).

The abovementioned challenges hold students back. These challenges prevent them from performing well, finishing their degrees, and fully developing their potential. In line with Republic Act 7722, which mandates equal access to quality education and promotes student welfare, these issues must be addressed. Schools cannot provide real support without knowing what students actually go through.

To the authors' knowledge, no recent local study has been conducted at Eduardo L. Josen Memorial College (ELJMC) that specifically investigates the challenges faced by its college students. This study may help administrators, faculty, guidance counselors, and policymakers in crafting more targeted interventions.

In reviewing existing literature, previous studies that examine student challenges often employed either qualitative (e.g., Akhtar & Akhtar, 2024; Saeed et al., 2020; Wagner et al., 2025) or quantitative approaches (e.g., Dagdag et al., 2019; Dy et al., 2015; Aldabbus & Almansouri, 2022), but rarely combined both. However, integrating qualitative and quantitative techniques offers deeper insight and more valid results (Creswell & Clark, 2017; Fetters, Curry, & Creswell, 2013).

The present study aimed to address the aforementioned gaps by using a more comprehensive and methodical approach. Specifically, it examined the common challenges students encounter in college and assessed the prevalence of these challenges. This study offers a clearer understanding of college student experiences, particularly within the context of ELJMC.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

A mixed methods approach combines both qualitative and quantitative methods within the same study (Creswell & Clark, 2017). In addition, these research approaches involve integration of the qualitative and quantitative results, which helps researchers explore a topic in depth and then support their findings with measurable data. Data integration means bringing together the results of the qualitative and quantitative phases to better understand the research problem. Hence, this method is suitable in the context of the present study. Specifically, the study followed an exploratory sequential design (Fetters, Curry, & Creswell, 2013). In this design, qualitative data is collected and analyzed first, and the findings are then used to inform the development of the quantitative phase. Figure 1 presents the three major phases of the research process.

Figure 1. Phases of the Exploratory Sequential Mixed Methods Design Used in the Study

Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis

This phase aimed to explore the common challenges faced by college students. A total of 25 participants from the first to fourth year levels at ELJMC were selected through purposive sampling. While the orientation and consent were conducted in a group chat via Facebook Messenger, data collection was done through one-on-one private message interviews. Participants were chosen based on their willingness and the relevance of their experience related to college life. Each interview followed a protocol as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1. Online Interview Protocol

<p>Introduction components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome Message • Purpose of the Interview • Informed Consent • Language Flexibility • Option for Private Response 	<p><i>Group Chat Message:</i> Good day, everyone! Thank you for joining this group chat. I'm Sir John Kenneth Meradios, and I'll be facilitating our discussion today about your experiences as college students.</p> <p>This interview aims to understand the challenges students face in college. Your answers will help identify ways schools can improve student support.</p> <p>Before we begin, please know that your participation is voluntary. You may skip any question or leave at any time. Your responses will be kept confidential and used only for research purposes. By reacting to this message, you are giving your consent to participate in this interview.</p> <p>Feel free to answer in the language you're most comfortable with (Filipino, English, or Taglish). You may also send a voice message if you prefer.</p> <p>For your comfort and privacy, you may send your responses directly to me through private message.</p>
<p>Interview Question</p>	<p>What are the main challenges you face as a college student?</p>
<p>Follow-up Probes (if needed)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Would you give me an example? • Can you elaborate on that idea? • Would you explain that further? • Is there anything else?
<p>Closing components:</p> <p>Appreciation and Reminder</p>	<p>Thank you very much for your time and honesty. If you think of anything else you'd like to share, feel free to message me privately even after this chat.</p>

All collected responses were transcribed and organized. This served as the basis for coding and thematic analysis. Voice messages were also carefully transcribed verbatim. Thematic analysis was used to interpret the data, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-phase process: familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report. Codes were first assigned to recurring ideas or phrases, which were then grouped into broader themes representing common challenges encountered by students.

Instrument Development Based on Qualitative Results

The questionnaire for the quantitative phase was developed based on the themes that emerged from the qualitative findings. Survey items were constructed to reflect these themes. Many statements were adapted directly from the words of participants, while others were paraphrased for clarity and consistency. This is used to measure how frequently students experience these challenges in their daily academic life for the quantitative phase. A 5-point frequency scale was used for each item, with responses ranging from 1 = Never to 5 = Always. To ensure clarity and content relevance, the questionnaire was reviewed by two faculty members with expertise in educational research.

Quantitative Data Collection and Analysis

The quantitative phase aimed to measure how common the identified challenges were among a larger group of students. A total of 281 college students from ELJMC

participated in the survey. Respondents were selected through convenience sampling, and responses were collected using a Google Form shared online. Data collection lasted for two weeks. The responses were downloaded and organized in Microsoft Excel for analysis. Descriptive statistics were used, including ranking and percentage, with a particular focus on the number of students who answered “Often” or “Always” for each challenge. These values were used to determine the most frequently experienced issues among participants.

Merging Qualitative and Quantitative Results

Finally, this study used a merging approach to combine the results of the qualitative and quantitative phases. Data integration happened during the reporting stage to compare and connect findings from both sets of data. Merging as a way to compare different forms of data side by side to answer the research questions (Fetters, Curry, & Creswell, 2013).

In this study, the merging process was done through a joint display. A joint display is a table or visual format that shows the results of both qualitative and quantitative phases in one place. This makes it easier to compare and interpret the data together (Guetterman, Creswell, & Kuckartz, 2015).

Ethics

Participation in both the interview and survey was voluntary. Consent was obtained, and no personal data were collected. All responses were kept confidential and used only for research purposes.

Results

Table 2 presents a joint display of qualitative themes and quantitative survey results on student challenges. As can be seen, Academic pressure emerged as the top concern. The item “I worry about failing in school” had the highest response (88.26%), followed by exam overload (68.33%), academic expectations (62.99%), and performance anxiety (62.28%). In addition, mental and emotional health concerns were also common. Stress (43.42%) and low self-esteem (41.99%) ranked high, along with some reports of family (18.86%) and peer pressure (26.33%). In terms of time management, distraction (47.69%) and ineffective time scheduling (37.37%) were frequently reported, while time conflict and lack of focus also affected many. Furthermore, financial struggles were also reported. Budgeting problems (38.08%) were more common than lack of support (18.51%) or needing to work (7.83%). Lastly, learning difficulties such as weak writing skills (38.43%), unfamiliar topics (35.59%), and short memory (27.76%) were mentioned but ranked lower.

Table 2. Joint Display of Qualitative Themes and Quantitative Results (n = 281)

Themes/ Codes	Significant statements	Survey Items	%Often/ Always	Rank
Financial Struggles				
Lack of allowance	<i>Kabit na libre ang tuition at dormitory ay hindi pa rin kasya ang 1000 ko per week... (S6)</i>	My allowance is not enough to cover my daily school and personal needs.	24.91%	16

No financial support	<i>Wala po talagang support... nawawalan po ako ng ganang magpatuloy. (S7)</i>	I lack regular financial support from family or other sources.	18.51%	18
Need to work	<i>Kailangan po mag work to the point na nawawala na po yung focus sa studies... (S16)</i>	I take on work or side jobs just to support my school expenses.	7.83%	19
Budgeting	<i>Kabit kailangan mo na bumili ng ganito, 'wag na lang muna kasi hindi pa kaya. (S17)</i>	I have to adjust or sacrifice personal needs due to limited budget.	38.08%	9
Academic Pressure				
Academic expectations	<i>Dabil sa expectation ng ibang tao... kabit hindi ako takot mag-fail, nakakatakot ma-disappoint. (S13)</i>	I feel pressured to meet high academic expectations.	62.99%	3
Fear of failure	<i>I'm afraid of failing because the expectations of My Family is too high. (S14)</i>	I worry about failing in school.	88.26%	1
Performance anxiety	<i>Kinakabahan pa rin po ako at pinanghibinaan ng loob... nauunahan ako ng kaba. (S15)</i>	I feel nervous during academic tasks or performances.	62.28%	4
Exam overload	<i>Sunod- sunod na sched lalo na pag quiz... Labat ng subjects may quiz kami. (S5)</i>	I feel overwhelmed when I have multiple exams or deadlines.	68.33%	2
Mental and Emotional Health				
Family pressure	<i>They always expect a lot from me—parang wala po akong time para magpabinga or magcomplain. (S1)</i>	My family puts pressure on me to succeed.	18.86%	17
Peer pressure	<i>Madami kaseng nakaka apektado po sir eh, like peer pressure... hustle na po kase eh. (S11)</i>	I feel pressure from friends to do well.	26.33%	15
Stress and anxiety	<i>Stress is my most problem... to the point na naiiyak nako sa kakaisip. (S2)</i>	I feel stressed or anxious because of school matters.	43.42%	6
Low self-esteem	<i>Nawawalan ka na ng tivala sa sarili mo... mas naniniwala ka pa sa kakayahan ng iba. (S15)</i>	I feel like I'm not as good as other students.	41.99%	7
Time Management				
Time conflict	<i>May mga gawain na nasasabay kaya di agad nagagawa yung school work. (S2)</i>	I struggle to balance my time between school and other responsibilities.	37.01%	11
Lack of focus	<i>Mas inuuna ko gumamit ng cellphone instead of doing my schoolworks. (S4)</i>	I find it hard to stay focused when studying.	32.74%	13
Ineffective time scheduling	<i>Sumosobra ako sa allotted time... nagugulo yung schedule ko. (S4)</i>	I often end up studying at the last minute.	37.37%	10
Distraction	<i>Ung attention span ko is mabilis mawala... nawawala ung attention ko. (S4)</i>	I get distracted by my phone, social media, or other things while studying.	47.69%	5
Learning Difficulties				
Unfamiliar topics	<i>Nabibirapan ako kasi stranger sakin yun eh like wala akong background... (S8)</i>	I find it hard to understand topics that are new to me.	35.59%	12
Weak writing	<i>Hirap po akong makapag-formulate agad ng mga word lalo na po kung on the spot essay... (S19)</i>	I struggle when writing essays or explaining my ideas clearly.	38.43%	8
Short memory	<i>Mabilis makalimot kabit ka didiscuss palang... (S18)</i>	I forget lessons soon after learning them.	27.76%	14

Figure 2 shows the percentage distribution of student-reported challenges per thematic code, as summarized in Table 2, allowing for quick visual inspection of the most and least prevalent issues.

Figure 2. Visual Summary of Thematic Codes and Their Reported Prevalence Among Students

Discussion

This study sought to identify the most common challenges faced by college students. The results revealed that financial, academic, mental-emotional, and time management issues were prevalent, with unexpected concerns over academic skills such as writing and content familiarity.

One of the most dominant themes was academic stress, especially fear of failure and exam overload. This supports previous findings where students report anxiety, cognitive overload, and performance-related worries (Dy et al., 2015; Saeed et al., 2020; Rabbi & Islam, 2024). Such pressure stems from heavy workloads, multiple deadlines, and the desire to meet expectations from family or school. Fear of disappointing others was also evident in both quantitative responses and student narratives.

In connection with academic stress, mental and emotional health concerns emerged, such as low self-esteem and high stress levels. This aligns with studies reporting that academic demands can lead to anxiety, emotional exhaustion, and even depressive symptoms (Pedrelli et al., 2015; Wagner et al., 2025). As one student said, “Stress is my most problem... naiiyak nako sa kakaisip,” which reflects the emotional burden students carry daily.

Another challenge involved time management and focus, with students reporting issues like distractions and poor scheduling. Prior research noted that juggling

academic, personal, and sometimes organizational roles leads to role overload and weak time management (Saeed et al., 2020; Fook & Sidhu, 2015). The inability to balance responsibilities often results in poor academic performance and elevated stress.

Though not the most frequent, financial difficulties were still a notable theme. Students reported budgeting challenges and lack of allowance, consistent with studies linking financial constraints to academic disengagement and mental strain (Dagdag et al., 2019; Moore et al., 2021). While fewer students reported needing to work, even modest financial stressors can disrupt focus and motivation.

Lastly, students shared struggles related to learning and comprehension, including weak writing skills and difficulty understanding unfamiliar topics. This reflects known barriers among EFL students and learners with limited academic preparation (Aldabbus & Almansouri, 2022; Schneider & Simonsmeier, 2025). Without sufficient scaffolding, students may fall behind and lose confidence in their abilities.

These findings support the need to revisit and enhance student support mechanisms. CHED's commitment to equitable, quality, and inclusive education aligns with the importance of addressing the identified concerns. As these issues persist, schools must take active steps to identify at-risk students early and design targeted interventions. As literature shows, when support systems are responsive, student success becomes more achievable (Akhtar & Akhtar, 2024; Wagner et al., 2025).

The challenges identified in this study should be understood in relation to ELJMC's unique context. The ELJMC known as "Kolehiyong Pambayan" and home of "Iskolar ng Bayan," provides free education to many students who come from low-income families. Because of this, it's not a surprise that financial struggles would appear in the findings. However, financial issues were not the most reported challenge. Instead, academic pressure stood out. This can be explained by the college's strong commitment to excellence. ELJMC is recognized nationally for its quality programs and top rankings in teacher licensure exams (PRC, 2023; PRC, 2025). Because of this reputation, students may feel pressure to meet high standards set by the school, as well as expectations from their families and communities. The results confirmed this, showing that students often deal with fear of failure, stress, and anxiety.

What was unexpected, however, were the concerns about weak writing skills and difficulty remembering or understanding topics. This was surprising because the college is known for producing high-performing graduates. These results suggest that while the institution upholds high academic standards, some students may enter college without strong academic foundations. This gap might affect how they perform in class and could increase stress. It also points to a need for more support in developing academic skills, especially in writing and content mastery.

While the scope of the present study focused on one institution, the findings offer a basis for reflection and action, especially for other educational settings. Hence, future research may explore how these challenges vary across academic programs, year levels, or institutional types. Moreover, determining which of these challenges most significantly affects students' academic performance, emotional health, and overall well-being. Such efforts would contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of student experiences in Philippine higher education, which may inform more inclusive educational support programs.

Conclusion

This study sheds light on the challenges students encounter in higher education today. This paper pointed out common stressors, such as academic overload, mental and emotional strain, poor time management, and financial difficulties, which emphasize the need for a more responsive and student-centered learning environment. The study also uncovered unexpected academic issues, such as struggles with writing and unfamiliar content, which add new layers to existing discussions about student readiness and support. These findings matter because they draw attention to how student experiences go beyond grades or performance, which reflect broader conditions that impact learning, motivation, and well-being. Understanding these challenges is crucial for educators, policymakers, and academic institutions that aim to improve retention, engagement, and educational equity. While this study focused on a specific sample and setting, the themes raised point to ongoing issues that are shared across many educational contexts. Strengthening student support and listening to their voices remain key steps toward more inclusive and effective education.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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